

SATVAVAJAYA CHIKITSA- A SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO MENTAL HEALTH IN AYURVEDA

*¹Dr. Sarika Gaikwad, ²Dr. Riddhi Kulkarni, ³Dr. Rohini Sakhatkar

India.

Article Received on 26 Sept. 2025,
Article Revised on 16 October 2025,
Article Published on 16 October 2025,

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17472380>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Sarika Gaikwad

India.

How to cite this Article: *1Dr. Sarika Gaikwad, 2Dr. Riddhi Kulkarni, 3Dr. Rohini Sakhatkar (2025). SATVAVAJAYA CHIKITSA- A SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO MENTAL HEALTH IN AYURVEDA World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(20), 166-173.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Satvavajaya Chikitsa, rooted in *Ayurveda*, is a non-pharmacological psychotherapeutic approach focused on strengthening the mind and promoting mental well-being. It involves techniques to control and restrain the mind from unhealthy desires and attachments, aiming to restore balance and harmony. This approach is considered effective in managing various mental health issues by addressing the root causes of imbalances within the mind. In this article, Basic principles of *satvavajaya Chikitsa*, its therapeutic importance in various diseases, its techniques and its comparison with modern psychotherapy will be reviewed.

KEYWORDS: *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*, *Satva*, Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the ancient Indian system of medicine, provides a holistic approach to health that encompasses the body, mind, and spirit. Among its treatment modalities, *Satvavajaya Chikitsa* is a specialized form of therapy focused on mental health and the management of psychological disorders. This concept is primarily mentioned in classical *Ayurvedic* texts, including the *Charaka Samhita*. *Satvavajaya Chikitsa* is unique as it emphasizes mind control, psychological counseling, and cognitive restructuring without the use of medicines.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Charakasamhita with Chakrapani teeka

Ashtang hridaya with Arundatta teeka

Ayurvedic shabdakosh and necessary dictionaries

Articles and Journals related to topic
Internet.

Literature Review

Definition and Concept of *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*^[1]

The term ‘*Satvavajaya*’ is derived from two Sanskrit words:

Satva – representing the mind or consciousness

Avajaya – meaning conquest or control

According to *Charaka Samhita*, *Satvavajaya Chikitsa* is defined as

“*Manodharma grahanam yattat satvavajayam smritam*”^[2]

Which means controlling or restraining the mind from unwholesome objects.

This therapy primarily aims at improving psychological resilience (*Satva Bala*) and involves techniques such as self-discipline, cognitive restructuring, and positive behavioural reinforcement. *Mano Nigraha* (control of mind).

This mind control can be both subjective and objective.

‘Self-control of mind’ is one of the most difficult tasks and need a perfect combination of desire, determination and dedication. It can be achieved as per Lord Krishna in *Bhagavadgita* through *Abhyasa* (practice) and *Vairagya* (detachment).^[3]

The other types of *Mano Nigraha* which are physician’s interference with patients mind control.

This can be achieved by various ways^[4]

By regulating the thoughts process – *Chintya*

By analysing the thoughts and ideas – *Vicharya*

By channelling the presumptions with logical reasoning – *Uhya*

By polishing the objectives by concentrating on it- *Dhyeya*

By proper guidance and advice for taking right decision – *Sankalpa*.

Lakshan, Artha & Karma of Mana/Satva

Sometimes, one understands a thing and sometimes one does not. This proves the existence of the mind as a separate -sense organ. That is why, when there is no contact of the mind with the sense organs and their objects, no understanding of things can occur. It is only when the

required mental contact is there, that one can understand things. Atomicity and oneness are considered to be the two characteristic features of the mind.^[5]

The object of thinking, analysing, reasoning, meditating, determination and what-ever, is to be perceived by mind is its object. Action of mind consists of control over senses, self-restraint, reasoning, analysing. Beyond that is the jurisdiction of *buddhi* (intellect).^[6]

The same methods like *Dhee*, *Dhairya* and *Atmadi Vidnyana* have also been mentioned in *Ashtang Hrudaya*

धीर्धैर्यात्मादिविज्ञानं मनोदोषौषधं परम् ॥^[7]

Dhi (discrimination), *dhairya* (courage, strong will) and *atmadi vidnyana* (knowledge of the soul etc.) are the ideal therapies for the mind.

Dhi is the ability of the person to decide good and bad, *dhairya* is ability to adhere to the good, avoid the bad, and withstand difficulties with strong will; *atmadi vidnyana* is possessing or obtaining correct knowledge of the soul, of the aims and pursuits of the present life as well as of future life etc., in other words, a philosophical view of human life. These are especially of great value in the treatment of mental disorders.

Application of *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*

While describing the principles of treatment *Acharya Charaka* prescribes the line of treatment for *Manasa Roga* specifically caused by *Manasa Dosha*.

मानसो ज्ञानविज्ञानधैर्यस्मृतिसमाधिभिः ॥^[8]

1. *Dnyana* (spiritual knowledge or true understanding) - Providing the patient with the right understanding of their condition.

Includes educating individuals about *Dharma* (righteousness) and moral conduct.

2. *Vidnyana* (specific knowledge or scriptural knowledge)-Teaching logical reasoning and critical thinking to overcome mental distress.

3. *Dhairya* (patience or controlling power)-Strengthening mental resilience to face life's challenges.

4. *Smriti* (memory or recall)-Enhancing recollection of past experiences for better decision-making.

Helps in breaking negative thought patterns.

5. *Samadhi* (mental equanimity, meditation or concentration) - Focuses on mindfulness and meditative practices to bring mental stability.

Includes *Pranayama, Yoga, and Dhyana* (meditation).

Acharya Charaka has mentioned the following line of treatment for management of *Manasa Roga* which resembles the techniques of *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*

मानसं प्रति भेषज्यं त्रिवर्गस्यान्ववेक्षणम्।

तद्विद्यसेवा विज्ञानमात्मादीनां च सर्वशः ॥^[9]

1) *Ahitanam Anupsevana and Hitanam Upasevana*

One should strive for discarding *Ahitakara* (harmful) and adopting *Hitakara* (useful) after careful consideration. In other words, it has been advised that mind should be restrained from unwholesome objects and engaged in wholesome, which is in fact *Satvavajaya* or *Ayurvedic* psychotherapy.

2) *Trivarga Anvekshanam*

While treating the mentally ill person, the course of conduct relating to *Trivarga* i.e. three objectives of life viz. *Dharma* (virtue), *Artha* (wealth) and *Kama* (desire) should be attended because *Trivarga* is responsible for *Sukha and Dukha* etc. Therefore, contemplation of *Trivarga* is must, which can be attained by *Dnyana* (knowledge or cognition).

3) *Tadvidyaseva*

One should go in the service of those who are well versed in nature and treatment of mental diseases i.e. specialities of the therapy and the therapy should be done by them. It seems that *Satvavajaya Chikitsa* was done by specialities at that time.

4) *Atmadi Vidnyana*

One should attain the knowledge of *Atma* (self), *Desha* (place), *Kula* (family), *Kala* (time factor), *Bala* (mental strength), and *Shakti* (capacity). The knowledge of *Atma* (self) implies the knowledge as the 'who I am' and 'what is conducive to my health'. Similarly, the knowledge about *Desha* implies the knowledge of the locality and propriety of regimen prescribed in the local conditions. In the same way knowledge with regards to the *Kula, Kala, Bala* and *Shakti* also play an important role in the treatment of *Manasa Roga*.

Promotion of Dnyana (Cognition)

Dnyana (cognition) in this particular reference is used for the spiritual knowledge for all practical purposes. *Satvavajaya* is aimed at the control of mind i.e. one should keep himself established in his oneself after knowing the real nature of soul & attaining the height of spiritual wisdom. The methods for improving *Pradnya* (cognition) and its components like *Dhi* (intellect), *Dhriti* (controlling power) and *Smruti* (recollection and recall) are considered as a component of *Satavavajaya Chikitsa*.

The definition gives a lot of scope for expansion

“*Satvavajayah Punah Ahitebhyo Arthebhyo Mano Nigraha*”

According to above definition, *Ahita artha* and *Mano Nigraha* are important. *Hita* does not carry any special meaning, it just conveys that something is unwholesome to the other.

Artha It is a wide variety of objects each *Indriya* has its own object that only it can perceive, i.e. *Gandha* is the object of *Ghranendriya* etc.

Satva which is considered as *Ubhayendriya* has been referred to as having at least five *Artha*. Apart from these five, anything that can be perceived by *Satva* can also be included in this category.

It can be inferred that *Artha* can be either *Panchendriyarthas* or *Mano Artha*. But in *Satvavajaya*, it is quite logical to consider *Mano Artha*, though it may not be objectionable to include *Panchendriyarthas* because ultimately it is *Satva* that materializes the perception of the objects, not *Indriyas*. *Asatmendriyarthasamyoga* is regarded as one of the principal causes of disease.^[10] So, avoidance of *Ati*, *Hina*, and *Mithya Yoga of Chintya, Vicharya, Uhya, Dhyeya and Sankalpa* should serve to cure the Psychiatric disorders.

Asatmyendriyarthasamyoga (Incompatible contact of *Indriyarthas*) is regarded as one of the principal causes of disease (physical or mental). So, avoidance of excessive, deficient and or erroneous (*Hina Mithya Atiyoga*) usage of *Chintya, Vicharya, Uhya, Dhyeya and Sankalpa* should serve to cure the psychiatric disorders.

Psycho-supportive Techniques

Acharya Charaka has described several psychological supportive techniques, which all comes under the broadbased *Satvavajaya chikitsa* of. He advocates *ashwasana* (reassurance

and explanations). *Suhritvakya* (guidance and suggestion), *Dharmartha vakya* (education of individual and family), *Ishta vinashana* (verbal shock: milieu therapy), *Adbhuta darshana* (showing extra ordinary things), *Tadana* (physical shock), *Trasana* (mental shock), *Santwana* (rehabilitation and reassurance), which are also known as psychological intervention.^[11]

Ayurvedic Psychotherapy also utilizes the knowledge and principles regarding functioning of mind described in Indian scriptures, like Upanisad, Bhagwat Geeta, Buddhist Literature. If something favourable happens, we feel pleasure; if something unwanted comes, we feel pain. But such pleasure and pain are only momentary. When in both these circumstances, we are able to keep the mind steady and stable, we gain lasting concentration, which is a barrier to Psychogenic onslaught as well as es somatic disturbances. In the modern world, a variety of stressors lead to over straining of the mind and body, where the Satvavajaya measures are the only logical way to protect us from the stress related disorders.

While describing the management of *Unmada Roga* (psychosis), *Madatyaya* (substances induced disorders) and other ailments like *Jwara*, *Atisara*, *Hikka*, *Chardi* of psychogenic origin, *Acharya Charaka* has mentioned some psychological supportive techniques which can serve as measures of *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*.

Satvavajaya Chikitsa is used for managing various *Manasika Rogas* (mental disorders), including:

1. Anxiety and Depression

Cognitive therapy techniques resembling modern CBT (Cognitive Behavioral Therapy).
Focus on positive affirmations and self-discipline.

2. Insomnia (*Anidra*)

Use of meditation, relaxation techniques, and proper sleep hygiene.

3. Stress and Lifestyle Disorders

Counseling, *Pranayama*, and mindfulness techniques.

4. Addiction and Behavioral Disorders

Behavioral therapy through self-restraint and moral education.

5. Psychosomatic Disorders (e.g., IBS, Hypertension)

Mind-body connection emphasized through meditative and stress-reducing practices.

Comparison with Modern Psychotherapy

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) shares similarities with *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*, especially in restructuring negative thought patterns.^[12]

Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) aligns with *Samadhi* and *Dhairya*.

Psychoeducation and Counselling reflect *Dnyana* and *Vidnyana* principles in *Satvavajaya*.

DISCUSSION

There are many facets, dimensions and methods of approaching the mental disorders and treating them through *Satvavajaya Chikitsa*, but the foundation is to train the mind to keep away from the *ahita arthas* i.e. incompatible and harmful objects of senses and mind. This will eventually bring the mind under control, to the line of balance, to help one conquer the disturbed mind and get rid of mental disorders. It is said that the body is like a chariot, the senses are like horses, and mind is like the reins; only by holding firmly to the reins one can keep control. If we do not control the five senses, horses will drag us away. *Satvavajaya* therapy (directed towards these) enables one to have control over himself. '*Chittam Indriya Sarthi*'. In this way it is similar to the discipline of yoga, which is defined as '*Yogastu chitta vrutti nirodhah*'.

According to *Ayurveda*, *Adnyana* is the main cause of diseases and with help of *satvavajaya Chikitsa techniques* i. e. *Trivarga Anvekshanam, Tadvidya seva, atma vidnyan* we can attain healthy state.

CONCLUSION

Satvavajaya Chikitsa is an ancient yet highly relevant approach to mental health management. Its principles align with modern psychotherapy and mindfulness techniques, making it a valuable component of holistic healing. Future research can explore its scientific validation, integration with modern psychology, and clinical applications in mental health care.

Avajaya is available in Charaka Samhita. Even, this word is never mentioned anywhere else in the ancient literature. It seems that *Acharya Charaka* used the word to name the treatment of the diseases where *Satva*'s balance is interfered with. Hence, he has defined it as a method of controlling or restraining the mind from unwholesome objects. It can be achieved by increasing *Satva* to subdue the exaggerated *Rajas and Tamas*.

REFERENCES

1. M. Monier Williams, Sanskrit to English Dictionary 1st Edition, reprint 1995, New Delhi, Motilal Banarasidas Publishers, pages 1334. Page no.98.
2. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charak Samhita. Sutrasthan Adhyaya 11 (Tistraishaniya Adhyaya) verse no. 54 Chukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Page no.-205.
3. Bhagavad Gita, English translation, edited A.C.Bhaktivedanta Swami Prabhupada. 19th Ed Bha Vedanta Book Trust. 2002. Page no.345.
4. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charak Samhita. Sharirsthana Adhyaya 1 (Katidhapurushiya Adhyaya) verse no. 20 Chukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Page no.652.
6. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charak Samhita. Sharirsthana Adhyaya 1 (Katidhapurushiya Adhyaya) verse no. 18 Chukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Page no.649.
7. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charak Samhita. Sharirsthana Adhyaya 1 (Katidhapurushiya Adhyaya) verse no. 21 Chukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Page no.649.
8. Dr. Vishwavas Gaur, Ashtang Hrudyam by Vagbhat, Sutrasthan Adhyaya 1 (Ayushkamiya Adhyaya) Verse no.26, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi, 2017. page no. 13.
9. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charak Samhita. Sutrasthan Adhyaya 1 (Dirghanjeeviteeya Adhyaya) verse no. 58 Chukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Page no.-26.
10. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charak Samhita. Sutrasthan Adhyaya 11 (Tistraishaniya Adhyaya) verse no. 47 Chukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Page no.-202.
11. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Charak Samhita. Sutrasthan Adhyaya 11 (Tistraishaniya Adhyaya) verse no. 37 Chukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Page no.-199.
12. <https://aamjournal.in/fulltext/70-1339062656.pdf>
13. https://ijrar.com/upload_issue/ijrar_issue_20542696.pdf